

Reactions of Allylmetal Carbonyls of Rhodium and Cobalt with Carbon Monoxide and Hydrogen : New Catalytic Intermediates in Homogeneous Hydroformylation Reactions

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Reactions of the trihaptoallyls $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_3$ and $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ with CO and H_2 at elevated pressures in *n*-tetradecane solution have been followed by infrared spectroscopy under pressure using the $\nu(CO)$ region to identify carbonyl intermediates. Thus the rhodium complex $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_3$ is carbonylated reversibly to a new $RRh(CO)_4$ derivative [either $CH_2=CHCH_2Rh(CO)_4$ or $CH_2=CHCH_2C(O)Rh(CO)_4$] which is only stable at elevated CO pressures. Hydrogenation of $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_3$ also gives a new species tentatively formulated as the propene complex $HRh(CO)_3(CH_2=CHCH_3)$. A related complex, possibly $HRh(CO)_3(C_3H_4)$, is generated by the reaction of $Rh_4(CO)_{12}$ with C_3H_4/H_2 mixtures in the absence of CO; this species is an active hydroformylation catalyst under mild conditions. The cobalt complex $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ is carbonylated reversibly to $CH_2=CHCH_2Co(CO)_4$, again a species stable only under elevated CO pressures.

THE hydroformylation of olefins with carbon monoxide and hydrogen (equations 1a and 1b) is an important method for the manufacture of aldehydes^{2,3,4,5}.

Such hydroformylation reactions are catalyzed by certain metal carbonyl derivatives including those of cobalt and rhodium. The currently accepted mechanism⁵ involves the alternating production of 16- and 18-electron intermediates illustrated by the following catalytic cycle for production of terminal aldehydes according to equation 1a (for equations 2a-2h $M=Co$ or Rh).

Recent work from our laboratory has involved the use of infrared spectroscopy at elevated pressures to study the chemical reactivity of transition metal intermediates relevant to the above mechanism for the hydroformylation reaction. Our results in this area to date have been of the following two types: (1) study of the reactivity towards CO and H_2 of stable compounds modelling unstable reaction intermediates (e.g. metal alkyls)⁶; (2) identification, by their $\nu(CO)$ frequencies, of intermediates in the above catalytic cycle which are stable only under elevated pressures [e.g. $RRh(CO)_4$ derivatives]⁷.

This paper describes further results relevant to the identification of unstable intermediates in the rhodium-catalyzed hydroformylation of olefins. The intermediates in the catalytic cycle 2a-2h ($M=Rh$) most amenable to identification are the coordinately saturated 18-electron intermediates, namely $HRh(CO)_4$, $HRh(CO)_3(CH=CHR)$, $RCH_2CH_2Rh(CO)_4$ and $RCH_2CH_2C(O)Rh(CO)_3H_2$. A recent elegant study⁸ by Vidal and Walker using infrared spectroscopy at pressures in excess of 1000 atmospheres provides conclusive evidence for the existence of $HRh(CO)_4$ under these extreme conditions. Our previous paper noted above⁷ presents infrared spectroscopic evidence for the formation of an unstable $CH_3CH_2Rh(CO)_4$ by treatment of suitable rhodium(I) derivatives with $CO/C_2H_4/H_2$ gas mixtures. This paper discusses evidence for another of the above catalytic intermediates, namely $HRh(CO)_3(CH_2=CHR)$. The role of trihaptoallyl derivatives in this chemistry relates to the possibility of their hydrogenation to the propylene complexes $HM(CO)_3(CH_2=CHCH_3)$.

according to the following general scheme ($M = \text{Co}$, $n=3$; $M = \text{Rh}$, $n=2$):

However, we were led to investigate such hydrogenations of trihaptoallyl metal carbonyls only after detecting preliminary evidence for $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ in the reaction of $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ with $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixtures in the absence of CO.

$\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ as a hydroformylation catalyst.

Our studies in the high pressure infrared cell on the hydroformylation of ethylene by various rhodium complexes using a 1:1:1 $\text{CO}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixture indicated that diverse rhodium(I) complexes are active hydroformylation catalysts under mild conditions (e.g. 35° and 20 to 100 atmospheres total pressure) but that rhodium complexes with the metal in other formal oxidation states such as 0 [i.e. $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$] or +2 [i.e. rhodium(II) acetate] are inactive catalysts under similar conditions⁷. The results with $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ were somewhat difficult to reconcile with earlier reports^{9,10} that $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ is an active hydroformylation catalyst for 1-heptene and related liquid substituted olefins. The observed inverse CO pressure dependence on the hydroformylation reaction¹¹ suggested that a 1:1:1 $\text{CO}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixture might be too rich in CO for $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ to function as an active ethylene hydroformylation catalyst. Therefore the reaction of $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ with $\text{CO}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixtures containing variable amounts of CO were investigated in *n*-tetradecane solution at 37° and at partial pressures 12 atmospheres each of C_2H_4 and H_2 . The following results were obtained relating to the production of propionaldehyde identified by its $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequency at 1738 cm^{-1} .

- (1) No hydroformylation: $\text{CO}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixtures with the ratios 1.0/1.0/1.0 and 0.4/1.0/1.0 respectively.
- (2) Slow hydroformylation: $\text{CO}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixtures with the ratios 0.3/1.0/1.0 and 0.1/1.0/1.0.
- (3) Fast hydroformylation: $\text{CO}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixtures with the ratio 0.2/1.0/1.0.

Thus the maximum rate of hydroformylation was obtained under these conditions using a $\text{CO}/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ ratio of 0.2/1.0/1.0. Gas mixtures appreciably richer or poorer in CO led to far slower reaction rates. Thus our previous failure⁷ to observe ethylene hydroformylation with $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ was a consequence of using a gas mixture far too rich in CO.

These observations suggested that the reaction of $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ with a $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixture might generate catalytically active intermediates for the hydroformylation reaction. In this connection the reaction of $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ with a 1:1 $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$

mixture in *n*-tetradecane solution at 35° and 6 atmospheres total pressure was monitored in the high pressure infrared cell (Fig. 1). This reaction

Fig. 1. Infrared spectra obtained upon heating $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ in *n*-tetradecane solution under a 1:1 mixture of C_2H_4 and H_2 at 6 atmospheres total pressure (a) upper left: after 1 hr at 37°, (b) upper right: after 23 hr at 37°; (c) lower left: after 30 hr at 37°; (d) lower right: previous solution treated with a 1:1:1 $\text{CO}/\text{H}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$ mixture at 33 atmospheres total pressure showing the 1738 cm^{-1} band of the propionaldehyde produced by the hydroformylation reaction.

gradually resulted in disappearance of the $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ bridging $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequency at 1883 cm^{-1} with the production of a new species exhibiting $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequencies at 2075 w and 2026 cm^{-1} . The pattern of these $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequencies is consistent with that expected for a trigonal bipyramidal structure [with C_{3v} local symmetry for $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$] [Calculated from group theory¹² for $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequencies: A_1 (weak ir) + E (strong ir)]. Furthermore, in some of the better resolved spectra (e.g. Fig. 1, lower left) the 2026 cm^{-1} band assigned to the E mode is split apparently owing to some reduction of the local C_{3v} symmetry by the ethylene ligand. This new species, unlike the different species formulated as $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_4^7$, persists in *n*-tetradecane solution upon release of the $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ pressure. The regime of stability of the presumed $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_5(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ is quite different than that of $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_4$ [reported⁹ $\nu(\text{CO})$ in dodecane: 2070 m, 2039 s, 2008 vw] which is only

stable at CO pressures around 1000 atmospheres and presumably higher. A solution of the presumed $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ obtained by this method was shown to be an active ethylene hydroformylation catalyst using a 1:1:1 CO/ C_2H_4 / H_2 gas mixture for which $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ is inactive as a hydroformylation catalyst.

The following additional properties of the presumed $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ are significant :

- (1) It can be generated on a preparative scale by the reaction of $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ with a 1:1 $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4/\text{H}_2$ mixture in an autoclave in pentane solution at room temperature and 50 atmospheres total pressure. However, all attempts up to the present time to isolate $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ from its solutions have failed since it appears to decompose upon removal of the solvent.
- (2) Treatment with CO alone results in the regeneration of $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$, identified by its $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequencies. A possible mechanism for this process involves ethylene displacement with CO to give $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_4$ which would then clusterify rapidly to $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$.

Our inability to isolate the presumed $\text{HRh}(\text{CO})_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$ combined with the lack of suitable model compounds for a more detailed interpretation of its $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequencies than the general group theoretical arguments mentioned above has prevented us from identifying this substance by fully satisfactory and definitive methods. The studies described below on the reactions of the trihaptoallyl derivatives $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{M}(\text{CO})_3$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$, $n=3$; $\text{M}=\text{Rh}$, $n=2$) were therefore initiated in an attempt to obtain information on the analogous propene complexes $\text{HM}(\text{CO})_3(\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCH}_3)$ ($\text{M}=\text{Co}$ and Rh).

Reactions of $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ with CO and H_2 .

Successive stages of carbonylation of the 16-electron complex $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ are possible involving both 16- and 18-electron species (Scheme 1). The reaction of $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ (16-2 in Scheme 1) with CO was followed by infrared spectroscopy in the high pressure cell in order to determine which of the species listed in Scheme 1 would be most favoured. Thus an *n*-tetradecane solution of $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ (16-2; $\text{M}=\text{Rh}$) reacts with 274 atmospheres CO with disappearance of the $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ to give the following species identified by their $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequencies (Fig. 2): (1) $\text{Rh}_4(\text{CO})_{12}$ [$\nu(\text{CO})$ 2068 vs. 2042 s, 1883 s cm^{-1} ; triangles in Fig 2]; (2) a ketone exhibiting a $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequency at 1720 cm^{-1} [$\nu(\text{CO})$ expected¹³ for diallyl ketone, $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCH}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$; 1725-1705 cm^{-1}]; (3) another rhodium carbonyl derivative exhibiting strong $\nu(\text{CO})$ frequencies at 2022 and 2009 cm^{-1} [reported⁷ $\nu(\text{CO})$ for $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_4$: 2115 w,

Scheme 1 Possible successive stages of carbonylation of allylmetal carbonyls of the Co/Rh/Ir triad

Fig. 2. Infrared spectra obtained by heating $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$ in *n*-tetradecane solution under 274 atmospheres CO at 38° : (a) upper left: initial solution; (b) upper right: solution after 20 minutes at 38° ; (c) lower left: solution after 19 hr at 38° ; (d) lower right: solution obtained after releasing the CO pressure from the previous solution.

2037 s, and 2019 s cm^{-1} . The last rhodium carbonyl derivative could be either $CH_2=CHCH_2-Rh(CO)_4$ [reported¹⁴ $\nu(CO)$ for $CH_3Co(CO)_4$: 2105 w, 2036 m, and 2019 vs cm^{-1}] or the acyl derivative $CH_2-CHCH_2C(O)Rh(CO)_4$ [18-5 in Scheme 1; reported¹⁴ $\nu(CO)$ for $CH_3COCO(CO)_4$: 2107 m, 2048 s, 2026 s, 2007 vs., 1719 m cm^{-1}]; the ketone $\nu(CO)$ frequency concurrently observed at 1720 cm^{-1} blocks out the region needed to differentiate between these two alternatives. Releasing the CO pressure results in the disappearance of the 2022 and 2009 cm^{-1} $\nu(CO)$ frequencies with regeneration of the 2060 and 2000 cm^{-1} frequencies of the $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$ precursor. This indicates quite clearly that the species responsible for the 2022 and 2009 cm^{-1} $\nu(CO)$ frequencies is one of the more highly carbonylated allylrhodium carbonyl derivatives depicted in Scheme 1 ($M=Rh$).

These infrared spectral data provide evidence for the following reactions upon carbonylation of $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$:

Reaction 4b is more plausible than reaction 4b' since our previous work⁷ showed that $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_4$ rather than $C_3H_5C(O)Rh(CO)_4$ is formed upon reactions of rhodium(I) derivatives with CO/ H_2 / C_2H_4 mixtures.

The reaction of $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$ (16-2 in Scheme 1) with hydrogen was also investigated. Thus, treatment of a tetradecane solution of $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$ with 14 atmospheres H_2 at 39° results in gradual disappearance of its $\nu(CO)$ frequencies with the appearance of a single $\nu(CO)$ frequency at 2020 cm^{-1} . The appearance of this spectrum is very similar to that obtained from the reaction of $Rh_4(CO)_{12}$ with the C_2H_4/H_2 mixture (e.g. Fig. 1, lower left) suggesting its formulation as a similar type of rhodium carbonyl derivative. We therefore suggest formulation of this species as $HRh(CO)_3-(CH_2=CHCH_3)$ formed according to equation 3 ($M=Rh$, $n=2$). The extra CO required for equation 3 must come from decomposition of some of the $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$. In this connection significant amounts of metallic rhodium were found in the infrared cell after completion of the experiment.

Reactions of $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ with CO and H_2 .

The carbonylation of the trihaptoallylcobalt derivative $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ (18-3 in Scheme 1, $M=Co$) appears to proceed in a manner analogous to that of the related rhodium derivative $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$ (16-2, $M=Rh$ in Scheme 1). Thus, heating an *n*-tetradecane solution of $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ [$\nu(CO)$: 2063 m and 1996 vs cm^{-1} as in Fig. 3, upper left] under 173 atmospheres CO at 95° results in the gradual appearance of new bands at 2045 and 2022 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3, upper right) which persist upon cooling to room temperature under pressure (Fig. 3, lower left) but disappear upon decreasing the pressure to atmospheric (Fig. 3, lower right). The failure for an acyl carbonyl $\nu(CO)$ frequency around 1720 cm^{-1} to appear and disappear concurrently with the 2045 and 2022 cm^{-1} bands suggests formulation of this new species as the alkylcobalt tetracarbonyl $CH_2=CHCH_2Co(CO)_4$ (18-4 in Scheme 1, $M=Co$) rather than the acylcobalt tetracarbonyl $CH_2=CHCH_2C(O)Co(CO)_4$ (18-5 in Scheme 1, $M=Co$). The monohaptoallyl derivative

Fig. 3. Infrared spectra obtained by treating $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ with 173 atmospheres CO : (a) upper left : initial solution ; (b) upper right : solution obtained after heating to 95° ; (c) lower left : solution obtained after cooling the previous solution to 26° ; (d) lower right : solution obtained by releasing the CO pressure from the previous solution.

$CH_2=CHCH_2Co(CO)_4$ (18-4) is clearly unstable at room temperature and atmospheric pressure with respect to CO loss to give the corresponding trihaptoallyl derivative $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ (18-3) in contrast to the monohaptoallyl derivatives $CH_2=CHCH_2M(CO)_5$ ($M=Mn^{15}$, $CH_2=CHCH_2M(CO)_2C_5H_5$ ($M=Fe^{16}$ and Ru^{17}) and $CH_2=CHCH_2M(CO)_3C_5H_5$ ($M=Mo^{18}$ and W^{19}), all of which are stable at room temperature and atmospheric pressure with respect to decarbonylation to the corresponding trihaptoallyl derivatives.

The reaction of $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ with hydrogen was also investigated. Thus, heating an *n*-tetradecane solution of $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ (Fig. 4, upper left) under 137 atmospheres H_2 resulted in the production of $Co_4(CO)_{12}$ [$\nu(CO)$: 2063 vs, 2055 vs, 2038 m, 2028 m, and 1867 s cm^{-1}] at around 50° (Fig. 4, upper right). Further heating to about 100° under H_2 pressure resulted in decomposition of the $Co_4(CO)_{12}$ as indicated by the disappearance of its 1867 cm^{-1} bridging $\nu(CO)$ frequency (Fig. 4, lower left). Interpretation of the terminal $\nu(CO)$ region of the infrared spectrum at this point is somewhat uncertain but the $\nu(CO)$ frequencies not attributable

Fig. 4. Infrared spectra obtained by treating $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ with 137 atmospheres H_2 : (a) upper left : initial solution ; (b) upper right : solution obtained after heating to 50° for 1 hr ; (c) lower left : solution obtained after heating to 100° for 24 hr ; (d) lower right : solution obtained by releasing the CO pressure from the previous solution.

to unchanged $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ could correspond to those of $HCo(CO)_4$ of medium intensity or greater [reported²⁰ $\nu(CO)$ of $HCo(CO)_4$: 2118 vw, 2052 m, 2029 s, and 1996 vw cm^{-1}]. However, since $HCo(CO)_4$ is not likely to be stable at 100° and no CO partial pressure, formulation of this species as $HCo(CO)_3(CH_2=CHCH_2)$ analogous to $HRh(CO)_3(CH_2=CHCH_2)$ is more probable. In any case this species appears to persist to a limited extent when the H_2 pressure is reduced to atmospheric (Fig. 4, lower right).

The activities of the species generated from $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ under various conditions for the hydroformylation of ethylene have been investigated. Reaction of $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ in *n*-tetradecane solution with a 1:1:1 mixture of $CO/C_2H_4/H_2$ at 35 atmospheres total pressure results in the formation of $Co_4(CO)_{12}$ at 50° and the further conversion of this $Co_4(CO)_{12}$ to $Co_6(CO)_{16}$ above 100°. No evidence for the production of any propionaldehyde was obtained in this system as indicated by the lack of the characteristic 1738 cm^{-1} $\nu(CO)$ frequency of propionaldehyde. Thus $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ does not appear to be an active hydroformylation catalyst in accord with the non-involvement of (allyl) $Co(CO)_3$.

species in the catalytic cycle 2a-2h ($M=Co$). However, the reaction of $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ with a 1:1 CO/H_2 mixture at 136 atmospheres total pressure results in its partial conversion at $\sim 55^\circ$ to $HCo(CO)_4$ or $HCo(CO)_3(CH_2=CHCH_3)$ as indicated by the formation of the 2052 m and 2029 s $\nu(CO)$ frequencies (Fig. 5, upper right). This solution is an active catalyst for the hydroformylation of ethylene at 110° (Fig. 5, lower left and lower right) in accord with the well-known activity of $HCo(CO)_4$ as a hydroformylation catalyst and its role in the catalytic cycle⁵.

Fig. 5. Infrared spectra obtained by treating $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ with a 1:1 CO/H_2 mixture: (a) upper left: original solution; (b) upper right: solution obtained after reaction with 136 atmospheres of a 1:1 CO/H_2 mixture at 55° for 18 hr; (c) lower left: solution obtained by treatment of the previous solution with 30 atmospheres of a 1:1:1 $CO/H_2/C_2H_4$ mixture at 110° showing the $1738\text{ cm}^{-1}\nu(CO)$ frequency of propionaldehyde produced in the hydroformylation reaction; (d) lower right: solution obtained after cooling the previous solution to room temperature and releasing the gas pressure.

Experimental

The infrared spectra at elevated pressures were run in the previously described⁶ stainless steel high

pressure infrared cell with Irtran I windows and recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 281 grating spectrometer. Eastman highest purity *n*-tetradecane was used as the solvent for the spectra. The cobalt complex $C_3H_5Co(CO)_3$ was prepared by the reaction of $NaCo(CO)_4$ with allyl iodide in tetrahydrofuran and purified by vacuum distillation. The rhodium complex $C_3H_5Rh(CO)_2$ ²¹ was prepared by reaction of $[Rh(CO)_2Cl]_2$ with $(CH_3)_3SnCH_2CH=CH_2$ in diethyl ether followed by washing several times with water and vacuum sublimation onto a -78° probe²².

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